

CHEMISTRY OF VANADIUM. PART V. FORMATION OF COMPOUNDS OF VANADIUM OXYTRICHLORIDE WITH PHENOLS

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Two series of compounds have been prepared by the action of vanadium oxytrichloride on phenols in CCl_4 , one at the room temperature and the other by refluxing at higher temperatures. The properties of the compounds have been studied and their structures discussed.

No systematic work appears to have been done on the formation of compounds of vanadium oxytrichloride with phenols, substituted or otherwise, excepting that by Funk *et al.* (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1958, 296, 36). They studied the formation of compounds of VOCl_3 with organic substances including a few phenols, and obtained the compounds, $\text{VOCl}(\text{OPh})_2$, $\text{VO}(\text{OPh})_3$, $\text{VO}(\textit{p}\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{O})_3$, and $\text{VO}(\textit{o}\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{O})_3$.

The present investigation was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the formation of compounds of VOCl_3 with phenols under different conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Vanadium oxytrichloride was prepared by the method of Roscoe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1868, 21, 342) and purified by distillation. It was redistilled over metallic sodium and extracted with CCl_4 . The chemicals used were of B.D.H. or E. Merck's 'extra pure' quality. Phenols and nitrophenols were recrystallised before use.

Procedure.—Two series of experiments were carried out. In one an excess of phenol solution in CCl_4 was added to VOCl_3 solution in CCl_4 and the mixture kept at the room temperature for 8 to 10 hours with frequent shaking till the evolution of HCl had ceased with the separation of a precipitate. In the other, a mixture of VOCl_3 and an excess of phenol in CCl_4 was warmed at $50\text{--}60^\circ$ in an oil bath for about an hour and then refluxed at a temperature slightly higher than the melting point of the corresponding phenol till the evolution of HCl had ceased. The products obtained in both the cases were washed free of phenol with CCl_4 , dried at about $45\text{--}50^\circ$, analysed, and their properties studied.

Vanadium was estimated in dilute H_2SO_4 by reduction with SO_2 , removal of SO_2 by CO_2 and titration with KMnO_4 solution at 70° . Chlorine was estimated as AgCl and nitrogen by Duma's method in Gallenkamp's electric furnace. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated by the combustion method in a few cases. Colour and analytical data of the compounds in the various phenols are recorded in Tables I and II.

General Properties.—All the compounds are dark in colour, crystalline, insoluble in common organic solvents except ethanol and acetone in which these are sparingly soluble. These are also soluble in strong alkali solutions. The compounds obtained at the room temperature hydrolyse slowly when treated with dilute alkali solutions or water, and the water extract responds to the test of Cl^- ; but those obtained by refluxing are not affected. These do not give sharp melting points but decompose when heated.

TABLE I

Compounds of VOCl_3 with phenols.
(At room temperature).

Phenols.	Colour.	%Vanadium.		%Chlorine.		%Carbon & hydrogen.		%Nitrogen.		Probable formulas.
		Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	
α -Naphthol	Greenish black	13.01	13.13	9.16	9.14	C: 61.42 H: 3.57	61.80 3.60	..	..	$\text{VOCl}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O})_2$
β -Naphthol	Greyish black	13.07	13.13	9.17	9.14	..	..	..	..	"
o -Cresol	Greyish brown	16.26	16.12	11.19	11.22	C: 45.90 H: 4.46	45.50 4.42	..	..	$\text{VOCl}(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O})_2$
o -Nitrophenol	Dark brown	13.53	13.48	9.35	9.38	..	..	7.33	7.39	$\text{VOCl}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NO}_2)\text{O})_2$
<i>m</i> - "	Brownish black	13.51	13.48	9.34	9.38	C: 37.77 H: 3.66	38.04 3.70	7.35	7.39	"
<i>p</i> - "	Light black	13.43	13.48	9.42	9.38	..	..	7.33	7.39	"
2,4-Dinitrophenol	Greyish brown	10.92	10.88	7.61	7.57	..	..	11.46	11.95	$\text{VOCl}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{O})_2$
2,4-Dinitronaphthol	Reddish brown	8.91	8.85	6.12	6.16	C: 41.88 H: 1.71	41.63 1.73	9.75	9.71	$\text{VOCl}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{O})_2$
Catechol	Brownish black	24.01	24.23	16.94	16.87	C: 34.46 H: 1.88	34.21 1.90	..	..	$\text{VOCl}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2$
Resorcinol	Light black	24.04	24.23	16.93	16.87	..	..	..	..	"
Hydroquinone	Dark grey	24.28	24.23	16.84	16.87	..	..	..	..	"
Pyrogallol	Greyish black	22.46	22.51	15.72	15.67	C: 31.49 H: 1.81	31.78 1.77	..	..	$\text{VOCl}_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_3\text{O}_3(\text{OH})$
Phloroglucinol	Chocolate brown	22.57	22.51	15.70	15.67	..	..	..	..	"

TABLE II

Compounds of VOCl_3 with phenols.
(After refluxing).

Phenols.	Colour.	% Vanadium.		% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		% Nitrogen.		Probable formulas.
		Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	
α -Naphthol	Brownish black	10.25	10.28	72.38	72.58	4.16	4.23	..	..	$\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O})_2$
β -Naphthol	Dark brown	10.31	10.28	..	..	..	..	..	..	"
<i>o</i> -Cresol	Chocolate brown	13.26	13.15	64.62	64.96	5.35	5.41	..	..	$\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{CH}_3\text{O})_2$
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	Pitch black	10.57	10.60	..	..	..	..	8.67	8.73	$\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2\text{O})_2$
<i>m</i> - "	Brownish black	10.58	10.60	..	..	..	..	8.66	8.73	"
<i>p</i> - "	Deep brown	10.63	10.60	45.10	44.92	2.51	2.49	8.69	8.73	"
2,4-Dinitrophenol	Brownish black	8.21	8.24	34.43	34.90	2.01	1.99	13.61	13.57	$\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{O})_2$
2,4-Dinitrophenylthol	Reddish brown	6.99	6.56	..	..	..	..	13.75	10.80	$\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{O})_2$
Resorcinol	Dark brown	22.14	22.26	46.92	47.17	2.38	2.62	..	..	$(\text{VO})_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O})_4$
Hydroquinone	Shining black	22.08	22.26	..	..	..	..	..	..	"
Pyrogallol	Dark grey	22.21	20.15	42.35	42.69	2.41	2.37	..	..	$(\text{VO})_2(\text{C}_3\text{H}_3\text{O}_3)_4$
Phloroglucinol	Deep brown	20.02	20.15	..	..	..	..	..	..	"

DISCUSSION

An examination of the results shows that two series of compounds of substitution type are formed when VOCl_3 is allowed to react with phenols. The replacement of chlorine atoms takes place in two stages. At the room temperature two chlorine atoms are replaced by one molecule of a dihydroxyphenol or two molecules of a monohydroxyphenol, the reaction being completed more quickly with the former. These compounds may be represented as $\text{VOCl}(\text{PhO})_2$ with monohydroxy- and $\text{VOCl}(\text{PhO})_2$ with dihydroxy-phenols.

On refluxing three molecules of a monohydroxyphenol react with one molecule of VOCl_3 and three molecules of a dihydroxyphenol (except catechol) with two molecules of VOCl_3 , and chlorine is replaced completely. These compounds may be represented as $\text{VO}(\text{PhO})_3$, and $(\text{VO})_2(\text{PhO})_3$ with mono- and dihydroxyphenols respectively. The anomalous behaviour of catechol, with which no pure compound was obtained, may be due to steric hindrance, which is in accordance with the observations of Funk *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

The analysis of both the types of compounds obtained with trihydroxyphenol shows that only two hydroxyl groups take part in these reactions. From the experiments carried out it is not possible to find the position of free OH group, and therefore no definite formula can be assigned to them.

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